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Annotation: this article will provide information about the activities of art managers, their positions in the field of marketing, criteria that should be valid within the framework of their activities.

Keywords: Manager, marketing, marketer, Art, need, goal, facebook, youtube, Twitter, politics, brand.

Let's give a description of the word marketing before entering the topic.

Marketing as a type of activity it is a type of human activity aimed at identifying the need of a particular enterprise or organization, replacing, selling, buying products and meeting the needs and demands of the population through these processes. If we focus this on the field of culture, then in theaters marketers carry out such processes as studying the interests of the population, spiritual reservations before a performance that should be staged, monetizing existing repertoire performances through touring, monetizing theatrical resources (actor, planner, staff, props, competitive institutions, as well as institutions in need).

The purpose of marketing: to attract new customers for a product, brand or service, offering them a high consumer quality, while retaining old customers, is to meet their tireless changing needs. The institution is counted from the main "chess grains" in ensuring its financial stability.

Market i's main task: to determine the needs and necessities of each market, from among which their companies choose those that can provide a higher level of service than other competitors.

This is to increase the overall profit of the company by providing the institution with high-quality products and, consequently, meeting the needs of consumers.

Marketing is such a process through which new ideas are planned and directed to the full process, paid services are organized.

With the type of Marketing activity:

The labor market includes processes such as demand Extinction, Market Research, commodity research, research of competitive conditions, analysis of the form and methods of sales. It is to adapt this process to the field of theaters,

The study of demand is-what performances are studied among the population without the use of different styles;

Market research-today it is studied which theater community market is performing agile and cashabop performances;

Commodity research-before the marketer demonstrates the spectrum, he studies the quality of the product, the popularity, the interesting, the state of the audience, the inability to attract the viewer, and carries out propaganda processes, depending on the situation.

Studies the conditions of competition-to the theater team studies the action programs of teams that are competitive in the territory, region, region.

Analysis of the form and styles of sale – in this process, such styles as happy seat, lucky ticket, 4x2 are foiled from innovative ideas in order to attract the population to the performance widely.

We are talking about a profession that has changed the concept of work in the field of culture.

An ART manager is a professional who is responsible for organizing creative events. His duties include monitoring trends in the art market, advertising, publishing and printing business, cinema, etc. Art Management covers all the components of the cultural and educational sphere.

An art manager is a manager in the arts. It is a very flexible profession and a person with appropriate skills can work in different areas of art.

Art manager - although today Uzbekistan is a relatively new profession in the art market, it is considered a profession that has developed a lot in the world market and has its place. These professionals are able to make friends between art and business, combining love for beauty and developed organizational skills.

ART manager-responsible for organizing artistic production. It combines thematic knowledge about an artistic product with how to implement such a product.

When it comes to important aspects of Art manager:

- ✓ How to produce a product that is required by the target audience is to choose performers, give them tasks, check the quality of the work performed and evaluate it with a professional eye (for this, the specialist must have good knowledge in the technical part);
- ✓ How to bring the resulting product to the art market-a good understanding of how marketing works;
- ✓ The process in which the current demand in the art market is high is to constantly monitor trends and study their changes;

Pros and cons of the profession

On the negative side, no matter how paradoxical, but the minuses are the same as the plus. dynamics and unpredictable. Stopping breathing can indicate complete failure;

On the positive side, constant development. The art market is as dynamic as possible, unpredictable, and if you stand in one place, it will soon leave you in the company of business and management. Of course, if you are a quality art manager, do a great job and understand where you are going, your income can grow exponentially. There is no ceiling, and almost everything depends only on you.

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